

Interplay of Structure and Agency: Women Survivors in Post- Earthquake Balakot, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: This article advances our understanding of the challenges and coping mechanisms of women survivors living in the Red Zone area after earthquake of 2005. These women were living in temporary prefabricated houses for more than one and half decade. 21 in-depth interviews, through purposive sampling, were conducted with the females. Following Naila Kabeer's perspective that women enhance their agency through pre-existing resources and achieve goals through family support, the study concludes that changed socio-spatial structure brought many challenges for women but through their active will, participation, resilience and family support they coped with the situation, increased their agency and became empowered.

Key words, Earthquake, women, Structure, Disaster, and Prefabricated

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1. Introduction

Pakistan is one of the countries in the world most vulnerable to natural disasters. It is in a seismically active area; hence its most severe and frequent risk is earthquakes (Ainuddin et al., 2013) (Halvorson et al., 2007). One of the most dangerous natural hazards in the country's history was the 2005 Kashmir earthquake that affected the whole Kashmir region and northern Pakistan (WB, 2005). Pakistan's province Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) and Azad Kashmir were greatly affected by this disaster in which 80,000 people lost their lives and almost 100,000 got injured (Durrani et al., 2005). Moreover, an estimated 3.2 million were either displaced or became homeless (Irshad et al., 2011).

It is estimated that across the world women are seven times more likely to die in disasters and receive little aid (Bradshaw & Fordham 2013). Women in most parts of the world are counted amongst poor, landless, malnourished and passive members of households and these pre-existing vulnerabilities are enhanced when a disaster strikes because their needs are not given much attention (Drolet et al., 2015).

Although there is an absence of gender-specific statistics for the Kashmir earthquake, several experts and international organizations believe that its impact was gendered, with larger fatality and illness rates for women than for men in all areas (IUCN,

2006; Enarson, 2009; Ferris, 2010; Hamilton & Halvorson, 2007). Relief activities after the 2005 earthquake were also not gender specific; neither there was any priority of the officials. Women survivors suffered in the relief period due to the neglect of sanitation and hygiene facilities, reproductive health care, and their access to relief commodities and compensation. Thousands of pregnant and nursing women faced health issues because their nutritional needs were unmet. (UNDP, 2006) These are the difficulties that women face during emergency relief periods. However, their suffering continued in the reconstruction phases, too, especially those living in red zones, who did not have a chance to reconstruct their homes to start the life they were used to before the earthquake.

Balakot, a tehsil in district *Mansehra* of KPK province, was highly affected by this devastating disaster and turned into debris, leaving many homeless. Initially people were shifted to the campsites and during the reconstruction phase prefabricated shelters were provided. The government announced to develop a model village for the survivors afterwards (Ahmed et al., 2008). This promise was not fulfilled after 17 years of the earthquake, and survivors still live in prefabricated settings.

Earlier researches presented that displacement from one's own place to prefabricated temporary housing due to disaster creates higher level of psychological distress (Fussell 2014; Yokoyama et al., 2014; Tanji et al., 2018). It was also documented that people who live for prolonged period of time in prefabricated housing face more mental health illnesses in comparison to those who live there for shorter span (Tanji et al., 2018). One of the researches conducted in Pakistan explored that the people of *Balakot* were unsatisfied with prefabricated houses. Reasons for this dissatisfaction were low quality of material used, nonprofessional and unskilled artistry, minimum community participation, lack of security, cultural adaptability, and climatic suitability (Ahmed et al., 2008).

Survivors make efforts to reconstruct their pre-disaster infrastructure and social structure to return to the familiar life pattern. It is a physically and emotionally tiring, time-consuming, and costly effort. This phase is especially challenging for women because of their different socio-cultural positions and the disparities they face (Ferris, 2010). As disaster impacts people differently, earlier research revealed that gender perspective is critical to understand in resettlement studies because disasters and all the aftermath of disaster impacts women differently (Bloem, 2013; Sohrabizadeh et al., 2016). Women experience challenges and cope differently depending on their education and social standing in the family and society (Hamidazada et al., 2019). Recent researches on disaster document that disaster is not merely an ecological phenomenon, it is also a social phenomenon associated with human agency (Perry, 2019). The researches related to Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) aim to improve the strength of nations to build resilience of the survivors to reorganize their livelihood. It is well documented in the research that although the vulnerability of women is enhanced within the reconstruction process after a disaster, but there is an opportunity to 'build back better' (Gull, 2019; Drolet et al., 2015). Gull (2019) documented that women of Kashmir used their resilience and actively participated in rebuilding the life after the disaster.

The existing literature mainly focuses on the emergency relief period, economic and psychological aspects of resettling at a new place. Socio-cultural aspects of coming back to

everyday life are not given enough importance. Similarly, little evidence is found on how local communities and women deal with their challenges after many years of resettlements especially those who are in a limbo (living in temporary houses for more than 17 years and hoping to resettle in permanent). To my knowledge, none of the researches explored how these factors became a challenge for women to adopt such temporary spatial structure with the hope of promised planned resettlement.

This article attempts to understand women's socio-spatial challenges after more than one and half decade of deadly earthquake and how the interplay of structure and agency dynamics changed women's capabilities to cope with post-disaster scenarios. This research mainly deals with challenges that women faced and what coping strategies, based on active agency, they employed to deal with situations. The challenges are further divided into two categories, 1) challenges of living in temporary spatial structures for so long, 2) challenges related to physical health, and taking on the active participation in economic pursuits to earn the livings.

2. Theoretical Viewpoints about Space and Women's Agency

According to Giddens (1984) human beings are purposive agents, have meanings and reasons for their actions but these reasons are grounded in the reflexive knowledge and continuous monitoring of actions through social practices. Therefore, human action cannot be understood in separation to social practice, likewise women agency cannot be understood and measured without taking into consideration the structure of the society. Agency has various connotations; however, in social sciences precisely, it focuses on the primacy and dialectical nature of human will in the social structure (Giddens, 1993) and has several dimensions (Ortner, 2001). In this regard, contemporary social theories are antagonistic to the liberal conception of women agency (Graham, 2000). For example, according to Khader (2018), the concept of 'agency' has predominantly aligned with empowerment since the 1960s, coinciding with the rise of feminist movements and growing advocacy for women's participation in development initiatives (Mishra et al., 2011). It is suggested that despite progress, women in many regions continue to contend with rigid patriarchal norms, remaining subordinate within societal structures, thus limiting their active agency.

Recent debates on women agency claim that agency cannot be measured without considering the cultural, social and religious context and measures of agency like education, health priorities, economic opportunities and making strategic life choices using active will vary across cultures and times.

A relatively recent case study on exploring the meaning of agency of *Qatri* women (Qutteina et al., 2019) concluded that agency has different meaning in western and non-western contexts. Saba Mahmood (2005) argues that liberal notions of freedom and individual autonomy may not appropriately capture the complexities of women's agency in non-western contexts. Naila Kabeer (1999) stresses upon understanding the nuances of agency not merely as a matter of individual choice but a result of the social structure, cultural norms and economic conditions. She highlights the importance of collective agency

which can be achieved through solidarity, mobilization and activism. Kabeer (2021) considers agency as a collective action that might be mobilized to promote women's empowerment, rights and gender justice. She presents that options, choice, control, power, and ability to make decisions, control one's own life and over resources are definitely defining terms for empowerment but for her empowerment is "expansion in people's ability to make strategic life choices in context where this was previously denied to them" (Kabeer 1999, 2001). Researches reveal that lack of economic independence due to limited access to education, productive resources, training prospects and limited contribution in the decision-making processes (Critelli, 2010, Sayeed, 2006) denied the women of Kashmir from opportunities to actively participate in the economy of household and these pre-existing vulnerabilities made them suffer more during the relief and recovery phases (ERRA, 2007, Gull 2019). Following the build back better strategy women were encouraged to participate in the recovery processes in their community and Kashmir earthquake provided an opportunity for the government and NGOs to start women's empowerment programs through vocational trainings (Hamilton & Halvorson, 2007). These opportunities (which they were previously denied) enabled women to actively utilize this human and economic resource to build their agency and strengthen their active will. Kabeer reinforces that all these factors (resources, agency and achievements) do not exist independently rather are interdependent on each other.

Source: Naila Kabeer (1999)

According to Kabeer resources are not necessarily the economic resources but they can be various "human and social resources" in the wider context which have rules and the individual using their agency (which is multifaceted) assign meaning, logic and purpose to their activities and achieve their goals. The present research explored how women of *Garlaat* (a union council of Tehsil *Balakot*, where this study was conducted) used their collective agency to overcome the challenges posed by the disaster.

3. Methodology

The fieldwork for the present study was conducted in 2018 -2019 in red zone area of *Balakot*. The rapport establishment and selection of key informants helped to break the ice and initiate the process of data collection. 21 in-depth interviews were conducted with women through purposive sampling technique. Most respondents were adults and married when they experienced an earthquake. Two younger respondents, ages 22 and 24, were selected concerning their involvement in welfare activities related to post-disaster temporary housing policies. Prior consent was sought from the interviewees.

4. Results and Discussion

Post-disaster People have different housing needs and these needs may vary over the time. Initially survivors need a safe place to stay, after the immediate response period need for proper housing emerges which is usually facilitated with temporary housing (Fernando, 2022). Provision of housing structure is very important because house is not only a space to live in, but it has multidimensional functionalities. These dimensions include, need for shelter, privacy, emotional needs, safe place for possessions, health and economic opportunities (Turner 1976, Fernando 2022). Disaster researches identified three sequential stages, immediate shelter, temporary housing, and permanent housing and emphasized on coherent approach in housing provision accordingly (Johnson, et al., 2006). The people of *Balakot* (red zone) are still living in temporary prefabricated housing structure.

Although disaster has no gender and no personal grudge, its effects are gender biased everywhere around the globe (Hamidazada et al., 2019; Sohrabizadeh et al., 2016). Women identified three key socio-spatial challenges, 1) Spatial challenges (Size of house, inappropriate material of prefabricated houses, and disassociation with the house, creating feelings of homelessness, privacy, and neighbourhood problems), 2) Economic challenges, and 3) health issues.

To deal with these challenges and adopt coping strategies depends upon several predispositions, such as the age of women, capacities, skills, experience, education, or interest, as these predispositions impact coping strategies (Sthapit, 2015). Women are not confronted with these challenges individually but all at once. Hence, the challenges, consequences, and coping strategies can overlap or influence each other. The current research argues that the following aspects of earthquake survivor women are significant and essential to understand their post-disaster life.

Spatial Challenges

Women are considered homemakers, spending most of their lifetime at home, especially in Pakistan (Zaman et al., 2023). Therefore, the spatial structure of a house directly affects their daily life activities, health, and socio-economic patterns. In the case of *Balakot*, post-disaster women found themselves in entirely new arrangements that made it a challenging environment for women to resume life in the prefabricated houses as an entirely new housing structure.

The Feeling of Homelessness Related to Prefabricated Temporary Residence

The people of red zone have lived in the prefabricated houses since 2006. Initially, they received the temporary prefabricated houses happily for many reasons, 1) at that time it seemed a best short term solution, people were not supposed to be displaced from their own area, as prefabricated structure was installed on their own land 2) it was an immediate relief from campsites where life was terrible for them, 3) people were facing aftershocks and the fear of aftershock as well, they were scared of the other housing materials therefore material of prefabricated housing was perceived as safe, 4) they thought that later they can

either reinstall these prefabricated houses somewhere else or rent them once they will resettle in permanent houses (which still could not be possible).

The temporary nature of these prefabricated houses and the hope of new permanent residence had made it challenging for women to accept these shelters as homes. The respondents shared that even after thirteen years (2006 to 2018, I conducted fieldwork in 2018 and 2019.), they did not feel prefabricated house a home. They shared, “thirteen years went by, but we still feel homelessness. We feel we do not have any home, who says that these platinum roofs are a house?”

Eighteen respondents expressed their grief “We are waiting for the government to resettle us permanently so that we have a home where we can resume life as we used to live before the earthquake.”

Vaccaro et al., (2019) argued that belonging is an essential human characteristic and perhaps a deep will that urges one to attach. The design of built environment anchors the feeling of belongingness and attachment to the place (Bergman, 2018; Dempsey, 2008).

Compromised Space for Women and Issues of Visibility

Due to the earthquake, women lost that private space and experienced excessive exposure to the outer world. The national and international communities reached out to help the survivors and left a long-term impact on the cultural notions of *parda*. Being patterned to live in gender segregated houses, the women felt like being uncovered in front of so many strangers.

Parda, or the privacy of a house, is an essential aspect of local culture, and women are susceptible to it (Zaman, 1989). One of the bigger challenges was absence of a proper boundary which deteriorated the privacy and enhanced feeling of homelessness. Lack of boundary walls resulted in discomfort among the community as they related it with honor and respect. *Shahtaj* Begum said, “This gift of government has made us shameless.” The lack of privacy and inability to move without *scarf* even at private spaces made women feel more vulnerable and distressed. The loss of private life at home made the situation more critical, the situations and outcomes that women tended to hide before the earthquake became visible to all. *Khansa* said,

“The house is associated with the private, things we never told to even our parents before the earthquake became the talk of the town now; I feel bad when neighbours listen to our problems and laugh”.

As a solution many women with the help of their male family members constructed either a boundary wall of bricks which was an example of women ability to work like men and this ability was explored during the emergency phase (Gull 2019). Due to lack of affordability some families still have hanged curtains around their shelters but the see-through materials could not provide feeling of security and comfort to women (Fernando 2022). *Sughra* said angrily, “this gift of government has made us shameless”.

Challenges of Living Space in New Spatial Structure

Another significant challenge for women in prefabricated houses was living space. This region has harsh weather in both summer and winter. The material of prefabricated houses becomes very hot in summer and extremely cold in winter, making the living condition more uncomfortable. *Kausar* shared, "We never thought that *Balakot* could be this hot; it is all because of these shelters; otherwise, *Balakot* is an icy area."

Women were unhappy with the size and composition of the house. The prefabricated house was smaller in size in comparison to their previous houses. Traditional houses in *Balakot* before earthquake were bigger and were gender segregated, men had separate drawing room (a separate room or an entire section for male activities) while the inner space of home was belonged to women. They could move freely and perform their household activities within that space which was abandoned in shelters home. Managing household activities, managing space for children and guests, elders, and other cultural activities like birth, marriage, and death rituals was a big challenge which only grew over the years. Initially when the prefabricated houses were allotted the families divided from joint to nuclear family system to be enabled to get this shelter but later the sizes of the family grew as they procreated and became overcrowded (Fernando, 2022).

The space of kitchens was multipurpose before earthquake; (other than cooking, as living rooms and guest rooms in winter). Women used this space to manage most of the activities which was not possible in prefabricated kitchens. Wood for burning fire could not be used and LPG Cylinders were not economically affordable. (Fernando (2022) also noted that communities which used firewood for cooking purposes pre-disaster, during resettlement they were not comfortable using gas appliances because they neither had understanding to use it nor it was economically reasonable. The respondents coped with this issue by constructing new cemented kitchens after a few years, because the area was cold and electric heaters were also not affordable, even though any kind of reconstruction was banned.

Inability to host the guests from far flung areas due to limited space was another challenge for people and a source of constant discomfort. *Sabahat* expressed her emotions,

"Our relatives from Islamabad visited us in the summer, they wanted to stay here for a week and enjoy their vacation, but we did not have enough shelter to manage their five days stay. We felt humiliated, as we used to entertain guests for weeks before the earthquake.

In a culture where people have a close kinship system, such situations were troublesome and embarrassing for the women. Few of them dealt with it by renting houses in the city. *Mahnoor*, who shifted to a rental home shared her experience,

"Look, sister, we have a kinship system; we cannot manage our family system here, so we decided to move to *Mansehra* in a rental house".

Prefabricated houses were losing its durability and was a permanent source of stress for the women and they did not find a way out to cope with this challenge because of poverty. Few people have migrated to the other cities but many are yet waiting to be permanently resettled by the government.

Impact of Spatial Structure on Social Cohesion

It is a well-documented fact in the post-disaster resettlement studies that psychosocio-cultural dimensions of the displaced communities are not given enough attention (Cernea, 2000; de Wet, 2006; Mannakkara & Wilkinson, 2013). Gaurav Sikka also argues that "...a life with dignity for a tribal includes material goods as well as identity, culture and self-image" (Sikka, 2020).

Prefabricated houses were designed for nuclear family structure and were allocated accordingly. The size and style of the house created a divide in the families, and brothers separated their stoves. Most women lived in a joint family system before the earthquake, and this sudden change in living patterns affected their social cohesion and financial conditions. They stated, "*assi kanni kanni ho gaye aan* (we all have separated)". Although the people of red zone installed the shelters at their own land but many new families started living there and the neighbourhood changed. The women lost their social circle (neighbourhood), they used to share problems and find solutions in their group discussions but the limited space here limited this circle as well. New neighbourhood was neither welcoming nor the host community accepted new entrants as their own people which caused drift in the continuity of social practices and weakened the traditions. "Before the earthquake. we used to share each other's problem, sorrows and happiness's. Now everyone is alone, these shelters had destroyed our traditions; we are living a tough life."

The social capital plays a pivotal role during disaster days (Ganapati, 2012) but prolonged stay in temporary shelters impacts the social integration significantly and more self-centred approach towards life prevails (Sikka, 2020). As *Sabahat* shared, In the emergency phase people helped each other but later lost in life, now everyone is just concerned about oneself". This situation was mentally tiresome and physically exhausting because social support was minimized, the work load of women increased, in joint family system they used to share their household work load but in prefabricated shelters they were supposed to manage everything by themselves. The following case study of *Shabeena*, represents how the earthquake impacted the routine smooth lives of women.

"After shifting to shelter houses, it was tough for me to continue my job and manage my home as before the earthquake, I was living in a joint family system, and with the support of family, I was able to manage my home and professional life, but in the nuclear family, it became much difficult. I tried to find assistance for my household chores but could not, I decided to quit my job, the blessing was that I had 20 years of service and got a pension".

The families also dispersed from the original spaces after the earthquake, so no support was available even in the neighbourhood. Existing literature also informs that in post disaster resettlement, due to disruptions the social practices can never be restored

because people face many challenges in living away from their previous support systems (Cernea, 1996; Badri et al., 2007).

These women struggled to adapt their private sphere within the new housing structure. With time the men of the family started supporting women in managing household chores like bringing woods, fetching water, taking care of children when needed. Three women who aspired to live independently pre- earthquake, they were happy in nuclear settings because they feel themselves more autonomous and independent. The design, style and allotment procedure of prefabricated houses gave rise to nuclear setups, and women automatically found some space to practice their agency. It gave them independence and decision power, although now they are overburdened by the workload but do not have pressures of joint family system.

Health Challenges in New Spatial Structure

Natural disasters result in significant mortality, morbidity, and disability due to high numbers of traumatic injuries that severely impact the injured population's health and the affected country's overall health system. The earthquake of 2005 had a significant impact on women's health, and the new spatial structure enhanced this impact (Bloem et al., 2013).

The traumatic effects of disasters were observed in almost all women (Behrman & Weitzman, 2016). Thirteen respondents were on tranquilizers and could not sleep without them. Five respondents had the traumatic experience of burying alive in debris during an earthquake, affecting their physical and mental health. During fieldwork, I saw sleeping pills in most of the houses. They shared,

“We are still numb by the disastrous impact of the earthquake. All the individuals in our society are patients with psychological disorders; every woman is anxious and depressed”.

These health issues of women affected the whole family in different ways. It is another economic burden for the family as they remain under medication, affecting the mental health of other family members who care for the patients and the household's comfort. *Zaitoon bibi* shared that her daughter left her studies to manage the household because, “I am still not well”.

Living in prefabricated houses with unknown neighbourhoods negatively impacted women's vulnerable mental conditions (Fernando, 2022). They continuously compared their previous homes with these shelters even after many years, their living conditions made them feel hopeless, poor, and anxious (Cooper (2014; Lawrence (2012); Hartig (2003) also confirmed that community's health and wellbeing is affected by unsatisfied with building materials, design and living with stranger neighbours.

To cope with the health challenges women were actively taking care of their health, they expressed, “Disaster has taught us that health is a blessing, now we are more aware of our mental health issues also and we visit the doctor”. Nine women shared that financial independence gives them liberty to prioritize their health issues and seek help. *Sughra*

shared, "Now we earn and can spend on ourselves more easily than before, secondly our families also know that we will be earning only if we are healthy so they also support us when we are not well".

Economic Challenges: Struggle and Formation of the Women Agency?

One of the most prominent challenges induced by the disaster is economic challenge, pre-existing socio-economic system gets destroyed and previous living standards are often not met (Badri et al., 2006; Konig & Teman, 2000; Nayak, 2000).

The earning opportunities, live stocks and other natural resources were destroyed due to the earthquake. The situation was even worse in red zone for those families where male members were either severely injured or died resulting in deteriorating the economic position of the family. The women were pushed by the circumstances to be involved in paid economic activities to restore and restart the life circle and support their families (Ceylan, 2015). *Shahnaz* narrated,

"We are facing many economic challenges like we cannot think of constructing our own house as we cannot afford the construction expense. My daughter wanted to pursue higher education, but her father could not do the job, so she left education and started a job to run the house".

Fourteen women shared that the economic structure of the community has altered, pre-earthquake women were involved in the economic management of the household, the elderly women had the authority to manage the economic activities, managing traditional resources like bringing woods to save the expenditure of LPG cylinders, being involved in kitchen gardening to grow the vegetables for domestic use, doing knitting and stitching clothes for themselves and for preparing the dowry of their daughters. Through all these activities they used to save money and manage it properly. *Shahtaj Begum* shared, "earlier the role of men was to earn money and woman was supposed to manage the household, an intelligent woman knows how to manage the household expense, we used to make almost half of the dowry of our daughters at our own and men had no idea about that".

Post-disaster the role of women changes from food crop production to cash crop production (Cagatay, 2001), In *Garlaat* the mode of economic activity also changed, and the use of non-forming goods had increased resulting in more reliance on cash crop production. The sources of income have changed from one to multiple because their expenses have increased, inflation has almost doubled the prices of everything.

To mitigate the needs, restoring the household items and managing the expenditure women played an active role despite the socio-cultural restrictions (Gull 2019; Drolet 2015). The women were taught many new skills through vocational trainings by the governmental and nongovernmental organization to build their agency and to make them autonomous to take on the responsibilities and roles usually held by men. Majority of the women viewed women participation in economic activities a source of enhancing their agency, "When women actively participated in all the heavy tasks that were supposed to be done by men only, made people realize the strength of women that what they are capable off".

During emergency and rehabilitation phases, educated women became an example for the rest of the community because they took on multiple roles and were involved relatively in more income generating activities than less educated. This has inspired the community to give education to their daughters to be more efficient in difficult times. "Initially girls in our area were not allowed to get education after grade 10 but now parents have learnt the importance of education and they are very motivated to give higher education to their girls".

To earn autonomy, and make agency women have to work both at home and outside the home which brings many challenges for them (Zulfiqar, 2018). They became overworked. the resultant fatigue and the issues of working outside the home, new space, and new work dynamics and time management were the reported issues (Badri et al., 2007). Many women never worked before the earthquake and had no idea how to handle the ground issues of managing work related stress, therefore sometimes they became anxious, stressed, and lost their self-esteem.

Initially the women used to go in group stress management activities held by NGOs which helped them built their resilience and they managed to cope with the situations using different strategies. They joined professions suitable to their skill and education and culturally appropriate opportunities like knitting, stitching and making handicrafts. After being well versed with learning the work dynamics and managing the household few women started their own businesses like opening beauty *parlors*(saloon), vocational training and garment houses. McAdam, Harrison & Leitch (2019) claimed that women entrepreneur networks help women to acquire agencies that question the traditional status quo. One respondent, *Saira*, was involved in stitching school uniforms with uniforms retailers from *Mansehra*. However, the space of the shelter house was limited to do work efficiently, so her family constructed a cemented Kitchen of considerable size, which was a suitable open-air place to work. This example shows that women can manage the novel situation through different strategies. *Saira* stated, "The earthquake has shaken everything but made the women stand high on their own".

Exploring multiple work opportunities, migration, and adaptation of nuclear family system economically empowered women. This empowerment gave them decision power and confidence and boosted their self-worth. They took charge of the decision related to their personal life, family unit, and children. "Today's woman is educated and autonomous therefore she is being respected and her opinion matters". Pre-earthquake the women were restricted to indoor activities and they were denied with the ability to move freely but now they may move independently without being accompanied. The increased decision power and autonomy has garnered their agency to decide for themselves. For Bourdieu (1987), the agency is the bearer of action, and experience is essential to the agency (McNay, 2004) that cultivates freedom. Furthermore, the performativity agency is not conceivable without economic and political nexus.

Research shows that the relationship between agency and culture for women working at the managerial level, produces nuance of agency that interlinks structure and self by gaining emancipation at the cost of structure and conformity at the cost of agency (Uppalury & Racherla, 2014; Lee, 2019). The data shows that these women acquired their

agency as a process of exploring real world and they were provided resources by the society after the novel situation of disaster (Kabeer, 1999).

5. Conclusion

This paper presented the challenges faced by the survivor's women of the 2005 earthquake. The women had faced challenges in every sphere of life, from the little invisible, non-material to more considerable material losses. Loss of loved ones and loss of household was the most significant one. Living in temporary prefabricated houses for more than 13 years has impacted the women significantly. Their experience and memories of living in pre-earthquake homes, which were more prominent in size and designed according to cultural needs, made them not consider the prefabricated houses a "home". This generated the feeling of homelessness, feeling of being unsafe and unsecure. The change in the spatial structure and extended stay in the prefabricated housing exerted its own influence and the socio-cultural dynamics were strongly impacted. The previous researches reveal that coherence is highly needed in the sequential stages of providing immediate shelter, temporary housing, and permanent housing (Johnson et al., 2006). For accelerated permanent reconstruction many researchers argued that in developing country context, "temporary housing supplied by the formal sector is often not necessary and should be skipped altogether" (Johnson, 2007). The challenges faced due to the spatial structure support this fact that although ready availability of temporary prefabricated shelter was initially welcomed by the survivors but the process of permanent resettlement was slower down.

Other than the spatial challenges, drift in the social cohesion and change in the economic resources impacted the life of women. Nevertheless, this impact also produces a dichotomy: the earthquake brought relative freedom for women of a patriarchal society. This freedom yielded the capable agency of women through their everyday experience and adaptation of new life situations.

The women experienced a life-changing course as the aftermath of the disaster changed their position and role from passive members to active and vital members. The qualitative nature of our research also allowed us to document the changes in showing the resilience during and after disaster because resilience was emerged as "an adaptive capacity that counteracts women's vulnerability" (Moreno & Shaw, 2018). The women of *Garlaat* also faced many challenges. However, they enhanced their resilience and agency to explore their capabilities and expand their skill set through vocational training by living in an environment they never lived in before and became empowered (Kabeer, 1999). As Ahearn (2001) argued, synthesizing Giddens (1984) and Bourdieu (1987), "agency refers to the socio-culturally mediated capacity to act", likewise the women of *Garlaat* upgraded their position in the community through the available support system and transitioned their passive role of "victims" and "rescued" during the immediate emergency to the role of "active agents" during the recovery and post-disaster (Moreno & Shaw 2018). This was also learnt through women of Kashmir that disaster can be a "window of opportunity" for women and they can take on multiple roles actively and efficiently (Gul, 2019). This article reassures Kabeer's perspective that resources and agency are multifaceted concepts and

people assign meanings, logic and purpose to their activities and achieve their goals (Kabeer, 1999).

6. Recommendations

It is suggested that while resettling the physical structure government needs to ensure that gender-related concerns are given utmost attention. Women can manage the most damaged household; how can they manage it if their needs have been neglected? To face this challenge, from a Pakistani perspective, Hamilton & Halvorson (2007) suggest that the state should focus on pre-disaster training of women in various areas so that they understand their position and can manage it in bad times. Hence, strict policy needs to take gender issues on priority. The need of permanent housing and sufferings of living in prefabricated housing is impacting the mental health of people of red zone; therefore, it is suggested to provide permanent alternate solution to these people by the state on the emergency bases.

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